

Short communication

First record of three pterophorid species (Lep.: Pterophoridae: Pterophorinae) from Iran

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چکیده

ضمن بررسی بال‌پولک‌داران خانواده Pterophoridae موجود در موزه حشرات هایک میرزایانس که طی چند سال گذشته جمع‌آوری شده‌اند، دو گونه از جنس *Hellinsia* Tutt و یک گونه از جنس *Merrifieldia* Tutt شناسایی شدند که برای اولین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شوند. این سه گونه، *H. carphodactyla* (Hübner, [1813])، *Hellinsia distinctus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855) و *Merrifieldia leucodactyla* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775) به زیرخانواده Pterophorinae تعلق دارند اما در دو قبیله مجزا جای می‌گیرند. دو گونه اول به قبیله Oidaematophorini و گونه سوم به قبیله Pterophorini تعلق دارند. با در نظر گرفتن این سه گونه، تعداد گونه‌های خانواده Pterophoridae در ایران به ۹۵ گونه می‌رسد.

The subfamily Pterophorinae, with a worldwide distribution, is by far the largest subfamily of the family Pterophoridae (Dugdale, *et al.*, 1998). To date 92 species of this family are known from Iran (Lederer, 1869, 1870; Staudinger & Rebel, 1901; Zerny, 1940; Amsel, 1959; Bigot, 1968; Bigot & Popescu-Gorj, 1974; Hannemann, 1977; Arenberger, 1981, 1995a, 1995b, 1999, 2005; Burmann, 1986; Sutter, 1991; Alipanah *et al.*, 2003; Alipanah & Ustjuzhanin, 2005, 2006, 2013; Alipanah & Gielis, 2010; Alipanah, 2014). While preparing a list of the pterophorid species of Hayk Mirzayans Insect Museum, we found three unrecorded species for the Iranian fauna. They belong to the genera *Hellinsia* Tutt and *Merrifieldia* Tutt in the tribes Oidaematophorini and Pterophorini, respectively. The Oidaematophorini is the richest tribe of the Pterophorinae in terms of species numbers, while the Pterophorini includes a lower number of species (Gielis, 2011a). Based on the available literature, a total of 228 species of the genus *Hellinsia* have been described (Gielis, 2011a), of which nearly 8% (30 species) are known from the Palearctic Region (Gielis, 2003, 2011a). But the genus *Merrifieldia* is mainly a Palearctic genus which 20 species out of its totally 22 described species occur in this region (Gielis, 2003, 2011b). The total Iranian recorded species of the genera *Hellinsia* and *Merrifieldia* increases to two and

seven species, respectively. The newly reported species are as follows:

- *Hellinsia distinctus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)

Material examined – 1 ♀, Kermān Province: Jiroft, Dalfārd, N 29°00'14.3", E 057°36'45.3", 2112 m., 27.iv.2012, leg. Afsariān, Moghaddam & Mozaffariān.

Diagnosis – Wingspan 15-21 mm; forewing yellowish-brown, particularly brown in the basal parts, with a dark spot before the cleft and an oblique costal spot surrounded on both sides yellow; hindwing darker than the forewing. In the male genitalia, left sacculus thinner than the right one, significantly thinner than the aedeagus, and slightly longer than uncus; right sacculus process as a sclerotized denticle. In the female genitalia, corpus bursa with numerous needle-like sclerites in the lower area; caudal margin of sternite VII convex (Arenberger, 1995a).

Distribution – Throughout Europe (without any report from England and Spain) until well into the north, and east to Japan including Russia, Kirgizia, Afghanistan, India, China and Japan (Arenberger, 1995a).

- *Hellinsia carphodactyla* (Hübner, [1813])

Material examined – 2 ♂♂, 11 ♀♀, Golestān Province: Golestān National Park, Koylar, N 37°30'42.5", E 055°50'48.8", 1306 m., 2.xi.2009, leg. Ālipanāh & Buszko; 1 ♀, Golestān National Park, Ghushah

Cheshmeh vill. to Savār vill. Rd., N 37°31'02.4", E 055°44'43.4", 849 m., 1.ix.2009, leg. Ālipanāh & Buszko.

Diagnosis – Wingspan 16-22 mm; forewing yellowish brown with a brown spot at the base of cleft; costal margin of the first lobe with an oblique spot; hindwing and its fringes brown-grey. Crest, frons and labial palpus brown. In the male genitalia left valve wider than the right one; left sacculus shorter than uncus, wide at base and narrow distally at its half length; right sacculus with a hump-like dome. In the female genitalia corpus bursae without signa or sclerite, apophyses anterioris short, with bifurcated tips, and both of the forked ends bent (Arenberger, 1995a).

Distribution – Great Britain, Spain, Morocco, France, Sicily (Italy), Italy, Belgium, Luxemburg, Netherlands, Germany, Switzerland, Poland, Czech Republic, Malta, Estonia, Slovenia, Austria, Hungary, Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Macedonia, Bulgaria, Albania, Romania, Greece, Russia (Arenberger, 1995a; Gielis, 2003).

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- Merrifieldia leucodactyla (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)**
- Material examined** – 1 ♀, Kordestān Province: Saghez-Bāneh Rd., 10 km. to Bāneh, Gardaneh-e Khān, N 36°04'13", E 045°59'31", 1976 m., 26.-27.vi.2009, leg. Rajāei, Meineke & Hofmann.
- Diagnosis** – Wingspan 11-25 mm; forewing yellowish white, costal margin with a dark brown stripe extended to the tip of the wing, without breaking; hindwing brown, only white in inner margin of the third lobe; Upper side of the antennae covered with black scales. Abdomen yellowish brown with one central and two lateral brown longitudinal lines. In the male genitalia, left sacculus process claw-like, twice the length of uncus and bent towards costal region; right sacculus process wide, as long as uncus. In the female genitalia, signa thin, stripe-shaped and in the long direction of corpus bursae; abdominal segment VII on the basis, with two flap-like membranous projections in different length (Arenberger, 1995a).
- Distribution** – Throughout the Palaearctic region (Arenberger, 1995a).

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Received: 13 July 2013

Accepted: 23 October 2013